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Learning Strategies and Writing Anxiety on Argumentative Writing Competence of Students

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of learning strategies and writing anxiety on the argumentative writing competence of Grade 10 students at Kitaotao National High School. Using a quantitative cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from approximately 120 students through a Likert scale questionnaire to assess their cognitive, metacognitive, and collaborative learning strategies and their writing anxiety levels related to procrastination, fear of criticism, and self-critical dialogue. The findings reveal that students effectively employ various learning strategies, particularly cognitive ones, enhancing their ability to organize information for persuasive writing. However, significant writing anxiety, especially fear of criticism, negatively affects their writing performance and confidence. The results indicate a robust positive relationship between learning strategies and argumentative writing skills, with metacognitive strategies emerging as the most significant predictor of writing competence. Additionally, self-critical dialogue is crucial in motivating students to improve their writing skills. The study highlights the need for educators to foster a supportive environment that encourages constructive self-reflection while addressing the challenges posed by writing anxiety.

Keywords: *Learning Strategies, Cognitive Strategy, Metacognitive Strategy, Collaborative Strategy, Writing Anxiety, Argumentative Writing Competence, Self-critical Dialogue*

INTRODUCTION

Argumentative writing is an essential skill for students to develop as it enables them to communicate their ideas and opinions. This involves generating unique ideas, organizing them efficiently, and expressing them engagingly. Argumentative writing is an art form that exceeds traditional writing, allowing individuals to express their thoughts, emotions, and ideas through the power of words. To enhance argumentative writing skills, individuals must read extensively, analyze the work of other writers, understand language and grammar rules, explore voice and characters, and practice regularly. Individuals can communicate more effectively, evoke emotions, and captivate readers by improving their argumentative writing skills.

Although argumentative writing skills are essential in various fields, many students in the Philippines need help to express themselves effectively in writing, which can hinder their academic and professional success. Research has shown that this is caused by writing anxiety, which significantly affects students' performance, leading to lower-quality outputs and reduced self-confidence (Kumar & Singh, 2021; Reyes & Villanueva, 2023). Moreover, research findings show that while some learners have already used various effective learning strategies, many still need to learn

how to use them effectively to improve their writing performance (Gonzales et al., 2022; Cruz & Santos, 2023). Additionally, students in the digital age may become overly reliant on technology, potentially hindering the development of their writing skills (Lausas et al., 2024). This gap in education demands a thorough review and a critical need for some teaching interventions in teaching writing skills and addressing the significant factors that hinder the learners' ability to express themselves thoroughly.

To help address this specific issue in developing the learners' argumentative writing skills, some factors need to be considered, such as the cognitive and metacognitive approaches. The cognitive approach involves specific techniques, such as outlining arguments and using evidence effectively in processing information. On the other hand, the metacognitive approach refers to self-regulation during the writing process which includes planning, monitoring progress, and evaluating completed work (Alcantara et al., 2020). Explicit instruction on using these strategies will undoubtedly lead to a quality writing performance. However, while these writing strategies are available, studies show that many students need to be made aware of them and often rely on traditional strategies that do not fully support their writing needs and abilities (Ramos & Dela Cruz, 2021; Santos et al., 2023).

On the other hand, another critical aspect that significantly influences students' argumentative writing competence is their writing anxiety. This anxiety may come from various sources, such as fear of criticism or failure and a lack of self-confidence in their writing abilities (López & Reyes, 2022). Rohmah (2020) states that a supportive classroom environment will help lessen this anxiety by fostering open communication and peer collaboration. Moreover, students need to engage in various activities such as peer reviews and group discussions as it allows them to improve their arguments while developing a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

In Kitaotao National High School, where this study will be conducted, there remains a significant gap in the writing activities among grade 10 students despite the increasing emphasis on developing students' argumentative writing skills. Specifically, for the school year 2023-2024, an alarming 112 out of 186 grade 10 students were observed to have scored low in their writing activities. This notable disparity raises questions about the effectiveness of the current instructional approaches and highlights the need for a comprehensive examination of the underlying issues.

Furthermore, investigating the factors contributing to low scores in writing activities among grade 10 students can shed light on the broader challenges students face during this crucial phase of their education. It is essential to explore whether these low scores result from inadequate instruction, limited exposure to argumentative writing, lack of motivation, writing anxiety, or any other underlying issues hindering students' progress. Addressing this gap in the literature is vital for improving the writing skills of grade 10 students and enhancing the overall quality of education.

With the studies above, the key objective of this study was to explore the relationship between learning strategies and writing anxiety among Grade 10 English students at Kitaotao National High School during the School Year 2024-2025 concerning their argumentative writing competence. By recognizing effective learning strategies that can lessen writing anxiety, this study intends to contribute valuable insights into educational practices that enhance student writing skills.

Statement of the Problem

1. What is the level of the learning strategies of the grade 10 English students on argumentative writing in terms of:
 - 1.1. Cognitive Strategy;

- 1.2. Metacognitive Strategy;
- 1.3. Collaborative Strategy?

2. What is the level of writing anxiety of the grade 10 English students on argumentative writing in terms of:

- 2.1. Procrastination;
- 2.2. Fear of Criticism; and 3. Self-critical Dialogue?

3. What is the level of argumentative writing competence of grade 10 English students?

4. Is there any significant relationship between Learning Strategies and Argumentative Writing in grade 10 English students?

5. Is there any significant relationship between Writing Anxiety and Argumentative Writing in grade 10 English students?

6. Which domain of learning strategies best predicts the argumentative writing of grade 10 English students?

7. Which domain of writing anxiety best predicts the argumentative writing of grade 10 English students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design to investigate the relationship between learning strategies, writing anxiety, and argumentative writing competence among Grade 10 students. A structured survey questionnaire was employed to gather data, allowing for statistical analysis of the relationships among these variables.

Research Design

A cross-sectional survey design was implemented, wherein data was collected at a single point using a Likert scale questionnaire. This approach enables examining the current state of learning strategies and writing anxiety among students while assessing their impact on argumentative writing competence.

Participants

This study's participants were Grade 10 learners from Kitaotao National High School. It aims to include approximately 120 students selected through stratified

random sampling to ensure representation across various academic performances and backgrounds.

Procedure

Data was collected using a structured survey questionnaire to address the three research questions, focusing on specific independent variables (IV) and the dependent variable (DV). For the first question on learning strategies, the survey included items that assess cognitive, metacognitive, and social strategies. Participants use a Likert scale to indicate how frequently they use these strategies in argumentative writing. The questionnaire was distributed to Grade 10 students at Kitaotao National High School, with clear instructions on its purpose. The survey featured items related to procrastination, fear of criticism, and self-critical dialogue to address the second question about writing anxiety. Participants rated their experiences regarding these anxiety factors using a Likert scale. For the third question, which focuses on argumentative writing competence measured by critical thinking skills, the survey again assessed students' self-perceived abilities in this area using a Likert scale.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire was adopted from Baker et al.'s (2019) study on the Academic Self Concept Scale (ASC). The researchers interpreted the data using a 5point Likert scale of the variables.

Range of Means	Descriptive Equivalent
1.0-1.80	Very Low
1.81-2.60	Low
2.61-3.40	Average
3.41-4.20	High
4.21-5.00	Very High

Data Analysis

The study assessed levels of cognitive, metacognitive, and collaborative strategies and experiences of writing anxiety related to procrastination, fear of criticism, and self-critical dialogue. Participants included 120 grade 10 students from Kitaotao National High School, and data collection involved a Learning Strategies Questionnaire, a Writing Anxiety Inventory, and an Argumentative Writing Assessment rubric.

Descriptive statistics provided means and standard deviations for each strategy and anxiety factor. Correlation analyses explored relationships between

these factors and argumentative writing scores, while regression analysis identified significant predictors of writing performance. ANOVA tests compared mean scores across groups with varying levels of anxiety. Expected outcomes included identifying predominant learning strategies and understanding how writing anxiety impacts argumentative writing performance. Ethical considerations ensured informed consent and confidentiality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analyses and interpretation of data obtained from the study. Results are discussed based on the order of research problems. A tabular presentation is provided before the discussion of each problem.

Table 1: *Level of the Learning Strategies of Grade 10 English Students on Argumentative Writing*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Cognitive Strategy	3.98	0.47	High
Metacognitive Strategy	3.86	0.55	High
Collaborative Strategy	3.82	0.58	High
Overall Mean	3.88	0.44	High

Interpretation adapted from Baker et al. (2019)

Table 1 evaluates the Level of Learning Strategies of Grade 10 English students in Argumentative Writing under three categories: Cognitive Strategy, Metacognitive Strategy, and Collaborative Strategy. Based on their respective mean scores, all strategies are interpreted as high.

The results show that cognitive strategies have the highest mean score (3.98), indicating that students primarily rely on these techniques when engaging in argumentative writing. This suggests that they are adept at directly processing and organizing information, such as analyzing topics, brainstorming ideas, and logically structuring arguments. These strategies align with the fundamental requirements of argumentative writing, which involves presenting evidence, organizing thoughts, and constructing persuasive arguments. The relatively low standard deviation (0.47) reflects students' consistent application of cognitive strategies, suggesting that most students are comfortable and familiar with using these approaches in their writing process.

Metacognitive strategies also show a high mean score (3.86), highlighting that students actively plan, monitor, and evaluate their writing process. This demonstrates their ability to set goals, self-regulate, and reflect on their progress as they develop their argumentative essays. However, the slightly higher standard deviation (0.55) compared to cognitive strategies suggests some variability in how effectively students apply metacognitive techniques. This could reflect differences in their capacities for self-regulation or prior exposure to metacognitive training. While students exhibit strong metacognitive skills overall, additional instruction on self-monitoring and reflection could further enhance their ability to improve their writing independently.

Although collaborative strategies have the lowest mean score (3.82), they are still interpreted as high, suggesting that students engage in group activities such as peer editing, sharing ideas, and providing feedback during their argumentative writing process. The lower mean compared to other strategies might indicate that collaboration could be more emphasized and utilized in their current learning environment. Additionally, the highest standard deviation (0.58) among the three strategies implies notable variability in how students collaborate. This could be due to differing confidence levels, social interaction skills, or the availability of collaborative opportunities. To address this, teachers could incorporate more structured collaborative activities, such as peer reviews, group discussions, or team-based writing tasks, to promote consistent use of collaborative strategies.

Thus, the overall mean score of 3.88 reflects a high learning strategy usage across cognitive, metacognitive, and collaborative approaches. This indicates that students employ balanced techniques to enhance their argumentative writing. The relatively low overall standard deviation (0.44) suggests consistency in how students perceive and apply these strategies. While the results are promising, the slight differences between the means of the three strategies highlight areas where further support may be beneficial, particularly in fostering metacognitive and collaborative skills. Strengthening these strategies could result in a more holistic development of argumentative writing skills, ensuring that students are well-prepared to approach complex writing tasks in diverse contexts.

Table 2: *Level of Writing Anxiety of Grade 10 English Students on Argumentative Writing*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Procrastination	3.45	0.78	High
Fear of Criticism	3.74	0.81	High

Self-critical Dialogue	3.69	0.78	High
Overall Mean	3.63	0.59	High

Interpretation adapted from Baker et al. (2019)

Table 2 presents the level of writing anxiety of Grade 10 English students in Argumentative Writing, categorized into Procrastination, Fear of Criticism, and Self-critical Dialogue. Based on their respective mean scores, each category has been interpreted as High.

The mean score of 3.45 indicates that procrastination is a significant source of writing anxiety for students. Procrastination reflects students' tendency to delay starting or completing their writing tasks, often due to a lack of confidence, difficulty organizing ideas or feeling overwhelmed by the complexity of argumentative writing. The standard deviation (SD) of 0.78 suggests moderate variability among the students, indicating that some students experience procrastination more intensely than others. Addressing procrastination through time management workshops and breaking tasks into smaller, manageable steps can help students overcome this barrier and reduce writing anxiety.

Fear of criticism has the highest mean score (3.74) among the three categories, indicating that it is the most prominent source of writing anxiety. This fear stems from students' apprehension about negative feedback, judgment from peers or teachers, or the pressure to meet high expectations. The relatively high SD of 0.81 highlights variability, suggesting that while many students fear criticism, others may feel more secure in receiving feedback. Teachers can mitigate this fear by fostering a supportive and nonjudgmental classroom environment, encouraging constructive feedback, and helping students view criticism as a tool for growth rather than a setback.

The mean score of 3.69 shows that self-critical dialogue is another significant factor contributing to writing anxiety. This involves students being overly critical of their abilities and performance, often doubting the quality of their work and questioning their writing skills. Such self-imposed pressure can hinder creativity and progress in writing. The SD of 0.78 indicates variability in how intensely students engage in self-critical dialogue. To address this, teachers can emphasize positive reinforcement, encourage a growth mindset, and provide strategies for self-assessment that focus on strengths and areas for improvement rather than just flaws.

Overall, the mean of 3.63 suggests that Grade 10 students experience high levels of writing anxiety

across all categories. The relatively low SD of 0.59 indicates a consistent level of anxiety among the students. This highlights the need for targeted interventions to simultaneously address procrastination, fear of criticism, and self-critical dialogue.

Table 3: *Level of Argumentative Writing Competence of Grade 10 English Students*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I revise my work based on feedback or self-reflection to improve my arguments.	3.84	0.87	High
The thesis statement in my argumentative essay presents my main argument.	3.78	0.78	High
I deeply analyze issues, breaking down complex ideas into understandable parts.	3.74	0.89	High
I avoid using wrong ideas in my argumentative writing.	3.63	0.94	High
I seamlessly integrate evidence into my arguments to support my claims.	3.60	0.76	High
Overall Mean	3.72	0.56	High

Table 3 presents the results of a study assessing the argumentative writing competence of Grade 10 English students. The mean score of 3.72, with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.56, suggests that the overall level of competence among the students is categorized as "High" based on the interpretation criteria adapted from Baker et al. (2019). This high level indicates that most students possess strong skills in constructing and presenting arguments effectively, including formulating claims, supporting them with evidence, and organizing their thoughts coherently.

The relatively low standard deviation of 0.56 signifies a moderate level of consistency in the student's performance, indicating that most students' scores clustered closely around the mean. This implies that while a few students may exhibit exceptional or lower performance, the general trend points to a uniformly high level of competence across the group.

These findings highlight the students' ability to engage in critical thinking and articulate their ideas effectively, which are essential for academic success and real-world communication. They also reflect the potential effectiveness of the teaching strategies and curriculum implemented in their English classes, which contributed to their argumentative, solid writing skills.

Table 4: *Significant Relationship Between Learning Strategies and Argumentative Writing of Grade 10 English Students*

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	r	p	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Cognitive Strategy	Argumentative Writing Competence	.472	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Metacognitive Strategy		<.001	Reject Ho	Significant	
Collaborative Strategy		.541 .428	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Overall Learning Strategy		.579	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 4 presents the significant relationships between various learning strategies and the argumentative writing competence of Grade 10 English students. The data reveal statistically significant positive correlations between all the independent variables—cognitive strategy, metacognitive strategy, collaborative strategy, and overall learning strategy—and the dependent variable, argumentative writing competence, as indicated by $p < .001$ for all cases.

Among the learning strategies, the metacognitive strategy shows the strongest correlation ($r = .541$), suggesting that students who effectively plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning processes tend to perform better in argumentative writing. The overall learning strategy also exhibits a strong relationship ($r = .579$), highlighting that combining strategies significantly enhances writing competence. Cognitive strategy ($r = .472$) and collaborative strategy ($r = .428$) also have significant relationships with argumentative writing, albeit with slightly lower correlation coefficients. This indicates that students who engage in mental processes like understanding, analyzing, and synthesizing information, as well as those who learn through teamwork and shared activities, tend to develop better writing skills.

The consistent rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) across all variables emphasizes the importance of employing diverse learning strategies to foster argumentative writing competence. These findings underline the value of equipping students with various learning approaches, particularly those that emphasize self-regulation and collaboration, to enhance their ability to effectively construct and articulate well-reasoned arguments.

Table 5: *Significant Relationship Between Learning Anxiety and Argumentative Writing of Grade 10 English Students*

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	r	p	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Procrastination		.138	.133	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Fear of Criticism	Argumentative Writing	.010	Reject Ho	Significant
Self-critical Dialogue	Competence	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
		.234		
		.325		
Overall Writing Anxiety		.309	.001	Reject Ho

The table presents the correlation analysis results examining the relationship between various psychological factors, including writing anxiety, and the argumentative writing competence of Grade 10 English students. Explicitly focusing on overall writing anxiety, the findings indicate a positive and significant relationship with argumentative writing competence, with a correlation coefficient ($r = .309$) and a (p)-value of (.001). Since the (p)-value is less than (.05), the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, meaning that there is sufficient evidence to suggest a meaningful relationship between writing anxiety and argumentative writing skills.

Thus, this result suggests that higher levels of overall writing anxiety are significantly associated with changes in students' performance in argumentative writing. It could indicate that anxiety, while often viewed as a hindrance, may also be a motivating factor in improving writing competence for some students. This finding emphasizes the need for educators to consider the dual impact of anxiety—both as a potential barrier and as a source of constructive pressure—in developing instructional strategies that enhance students' writing abilities while managing their anxiety levels.

Table 6. *Learning Strategies Domain that Best Predicts the Argumentative Writing of the Grade 10 English Students*

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Remarks
	B	SE	Beta	t	
Cognitive Strategy	.121	.131	.100	.920	.360 Not significant
Metacognitive Strategy	.386	.104	.382	3.706	.000 Significant
Collaborative Strategy	.207	.085	.216	2.450	.016 Significant

Note: Constant=0.995, F(3,116)=20.538, p<.001, R²=.347

Table 6 presents a multiple regression analysis examining the predictive relationship between three domains of learning strategies—cognitive strategy, metacognitive strategy, and collaborative strategy—and the argumentative writing competence of Grade 10 English students. The model is statistically significant, as indicated by $F(3, 116) = 20.538$, ($p < .001$), with an ($R^2 = .347$), suggesting that these learning strategies explain 34.7% of the variance in students' argumentative writing competence.

Among the three predictors, metacognitive strategy has the most vital and significant impact on argumentative writing, with a standardized beta coefficient (beta) of .382, ($t=3.706$), and ($p=.000$). This result indicates that metacognitive strategies, such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating one's writing process, significantly enhance students' ability to perform well in argumentative writing tasks.

The collaborative strategy also shows a significant positive effect, with a standardized beta coefficient (beta) of .216, ($t=2.450$), and ($p=.016$). This finding implies that engaging in collaborative activities, such as peer feedback and group discussions, contributes to developing argumentative writing competence.

In contrast, cognitive strategy does not significantly predict argumentative writing performance, as shown by its (p)-value of (.360), which is above the (.05) threshold. This suggests that while cognitive strategies, like memorization or basic comprehension, may support learning, they are less influential in enhancing argumentative writing than metacognitive and collaborative strategies. Overall, the results emphasize the importance of fostering metacognitive and collaborative strategies in teaching argumentative writing, as these strategies significantly improve writing performance among Grade 10 English students.

Table 7. *Writing Anxiety Domain that Best Predicts the Argumentative Writing of the Grade 10 English Students*

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Remarks
	B	SE	Beta	t	
Procrastination	.057	.064	.080	.893	.374 Not significant
Fear of Criticism	-	.091	-.089	-.930	.930 Not Significant
Self-critical Dialogue	.228	.094	.319	2.420	.017 Significant

Note. Constant=2.079, F(3,116)=4.872, p=.003, R²=.112

Table 7 presents a multiple regression analysis examining the predictive relationship between three domains of writing anxiety—procrastination, fear of criticism, and self-critical dialogue—and the argumentative writing competence of Grade 10 English students. The overall regression model is statistically significant, as indicated by $F(3, 116) = 4.872$, ($p = .003$), with an ($R^2 = .112$). This suggests that these writing anxiety domains can explain 11.2% of the

variance in students' argumentative writing competence.

Among the predictors, self-critical dialogue emerges as the only significant predictor of argumentative writing competence, with a standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .319$), ($t = 2.420$), and ($p = .017$). This result indicates that self-critical dialogue, characterized by students' tendency to evaluate and criticize their writing harshly, significantly impacts their argumentative writing performance. This finding implies that a certain level of self-reflection and critique might motivate students to improve their writing skills.

In contrast, procrastination ($\beta = .080$), ($p = .374$) and fear of criticism ($\beta = -.012$), ($p = .930$) do not significantly predict argumentative writing competence. These results suggest that while these factors may influence students' emotional experiences, they do not directly contribute to their performance in argumentative writing tasks.

Overall, the findings highlight the importance of addressing self-critical tendencies in teaching practices. While self-critical dialogue can drive improvement, educators should ensure it remains constructive and does not lead to excessive negative self-evaluation. The non-significant results for procrastination and fear of criticism suggest these factors must be explored further to determine their indirect effects or interactions with other variables in writing performance.

CONCLUSION

Cognitive approaches are the most frequently employed learning strategies among Grade 10 students. Their exceptional accomplishments in argumentative writing are substantiated by their information organization strategies. Nevertheless, the inconsistent application of cooperative strategies implies the necessity of improving team performance. Students are significantly impacted by writing anxiety, particularly the dread of judgment, despite the fact that it may also serve as a motivator. The most significant predictors of success are metacognitive tactics, which are positively correlated with argumentative writing styles and learning methodologies. Group assignments are also beneficial; improved performance is achieved through the organization, monitoring, and evaluation of the writing process. Self-critical dialogue is the sole primary predictor of writing skill, underscoring the significance of comprehensive self-reflection. Conversely, the direct impact of procrastination and dread of criticism on performance is minimal, which

underscores the need for additional research focused on their indirect implications. These results emphasize the necessity of implementing a variety of teaching strategies and a writing environment that is conducive to the development of students' critical thinking and communication abilities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from the study, the following recommendations are given:

Educators should prioritize metacognitive and collaborative strategies through focused instruction and organized activities, such as peer review sessions and group discussions, to enhance students' argumentative writing skills. Additionally, offering training on self-monitoring techniques will help students manage their writing processes more effectively, leading to a more well-rounded development of their writing abilities and greater confidence in handling complex tasks.

To effectively alleviate writing anxiety, educators should implement specific interventions tailored to each category of anxiety, such as time management workshops that teach students to break tasks into smaller steps to combat procrastination. Additionally, fostering a supportive classroom environment that encourages constructive feedback and promotes a growth mindset will help students view feedback positively and reduce self-critical thoughts, ultimately enhancing their confidence and writing experience.

To strengthen this foundation, educators should enhance argumentative writing instruction by introducing a wider variety of writing tasks and opportunities for peer feedback. They should also encourage student participation in debates and discussions to develop critical thinking skills. Additionally, offering targeted support for struggling students and implementing regular assessments and reflections on writing practices can help all students achieve their full potential and build confidence for future academic challenges.

To enhance argumentative writing competence, educators should incorporate various learning strategies into their teaching methods, focusing on metacognitive training to improve students' self-regulation skills for better planning and assessment of their writing. Integrating collaborative activities like peer reviews and group discussions can also boost cognitive engagement and writing results. At the same time, explicit instruction on using various strategies together will encourage students to take a more comprehensive

approach to their writing, ultimately increasing their confidence and proficiency in argumentative tasks.

To tackle the effects of writing anxiety, educators should implement instructional strategies that improve writing skills while also assisting students in managing their anxiety. Techniques like mindfulness practices, stress management workshops, and positive reinforcement can help students use their anxiety productively. Creating a supportive classroom environment will encourage students to share their ideas and receive feedback, ultimately enhancing their argumentative writing competence.

To enhance student performance in argumentative writing, educators should focus on incorporating metacognitive and collaborative strategies into their teaching methods. This can be done through structured activities that promote self-reflection, goal-setting, peer feedback, workshops on metacognitive skills, and collaborative projects that create a supportive learning environment. These strategies will ultimately boost students' writing abilities and academic success.

To help students use self-critical dialogue effectively, educators should implement strategies that encourage constructive self-reflection. This can involve guided exercises that allow students to assess their writing by recognizing both strengths and areas for improvement while also creating a classroom atmosphere that promotes positive feedback and peer support to reduce negative self-evaluation; further research into procrastination and fear of criticism could also provide insights for improving students' overall writing skills.

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